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THEODORA VARDOULI, *GRAPH VISION: DIGITAL ARCHITECTURE'S SKELETONS*, THE MIT PRESS, CAMBRIDGE, MASS., 2024.

Graph Vision provides a historical overview of the introduction of graphs in architecture and urban design. Schematically, graphs are mathematical tools that pertain to the branch of finite mathematics. Through a simple language of nodes and edges, graphs can chart out and count the relations between objects. They do not describe the visual properties of objects, rather how they relate and structure. As abstract mathematical tools, their application to architecture does not concern the actual building, but rather its representation; in other words, graphs can only be used in the design process. Applied to plans, graphs could represent rooms as nodes and connections between spaces as edges. The implications of this simple move were however profound: rather than representing the geometrical qualities of buildings, graphs captured their structural relations such as the circulation layout and the overall arrangement of rooms. They attended to the desire to apply mathematical methods to architecture and, due to the potentially large amount of calculations involved in manipulating plans through graphs, mainframe computers became the ideal instruments to support such project. As Vardouli reminds us, graphs provided the foundations for what would eventually become known as digital architecture.

A large part of the book is dedicated to the pioneers of this line of research: Lionel March, Philip Steadman, and Philip Tabor at the Centre for Land Use and Built Form Studies (LUBFS) at Cambridge University, Yona Friedman, operating between France and the USA, Christopher Alexander, Nicholas Negroponce, and William Mitchell. The survey operated by Vardouli concludes at the end of the 1970s and therefore does not assess the work of Bill Hillier and his UCL-based group Space Syntax.

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Around these central figures, Vardouli reconstructs a carefully and lesser known network of collaborators, artists, philosophers, and mathematicians that contributed in different ways to the development of a graph-based architecture. The vast majority of the research on graphs took place in the Anglo-Saxon world, with some exceptions such as the work carried out by Yona Friedman in France.

The book, an elegant and meticulously designed object, is structured into three main parts, plus a conclusion: “Images,” “Tools,” “Infrastructure,” and “Skeletons.” The first section traces the attempts—mainly by Lionel March and Philip Steadman—to introduce graphs to develop a scientific approach to design. Vardouli unfolds the different roles played by graphs in this context. They were mobilised to do away with, or at least diminish, the importance of form as well as the visual and geometrical aspects of design, in favour of structural and organisational characters (Lionel March and Ray Matela maintained that graphs were immune to geometrical considerations). Regardless of the initial ambitions, graphs themselves were visual artefacts whose abstract aesthetic was, and still is, very enticing. Minimal representations of plans as graphs or large catalogues of combinations of rooms also fascinated architects. “Tools” surveys the many attempts to implement graphs in architectural design to analyse and automatically generate plans. The discussion uncovers the issues emerging from striking a balance between the whole set of parameters informing a particular layout and the limitations provided by graphs. Finally, “Infrastructure” describes how graphs enhanced participation by either involving end users or providing an exhaustive catalogue of all possible plans based on a single graph for users to select from.

To grasp the novelty ushered by the introduction of graphs in design, it suffices to point out that only a couple of years earlier Le Corbusier’s major works on mathematics and architecture—*Modulor* (1948) and *Modulor 2* (1955)—were still based on geometrical proportions which he had broadly inherited from the renaissance. Tellingly, the symposium held at the Triennale in Milan in 1951 to discuss and validate Le Corbusier’s *Modulor* was titled *La Divina Proporzione* [The Divine Proportion], a direct homage to Luca Pacioli.¹

Through the figure of the graph, Vardouli unfolds a rich aesthetic, social, technological, and political debate that animated the architectural discourse from the late 1950s until the 1980s. Some of the factors that

¹ A. C. Cimoli, F. Irace (eds.), *La divina proporzione: Triennale 1951*, Electa, Milano, 2007.

drew architects to graphs were: the industrialisation of the construction industry prompted by the need for post-war mass housing, the importance of a socially-oriented architecture that paid less attention to form and more to program and organisation, and the possibilities provided by computers to manage complex tasks to develop a science of design. A particular political agenda that graphs elicited was that of participation: in experiments such as Friedman's *FLATWRITER* or Alexander's *Pattern Language*, graphs systematised the production of layouts—mostly for residential buildings—or urban spaces potentially bypassing the need to involve architects in the design process. Participation was perhaps an aspect of an even larger political agenda for design: as Vardouli notices, “graphs structured choice”² and therefore became vehicles for emancipation.

Though Vardouli's book has a clear historical focus, as for any historical survey, it is unavoidable to draw parallels between the ambitions of the experiments on graphs and the more recent or contemporary state of the discourse of digital architecture. By expanding the timeframe considered, graphs appear to occupy a peculiar position. Mario Carpo characterised the periodisation of digital architecture through two significant turns: the first one which took place in the early 1990s when powerful and cheaper personal computers came to fruition allowing architects to model complex geometries, the second which emerged some twenty years later when large datasets, i.e. collections of numbers, became available for processing. If the first digital turn largely concentrated on geometry, the second one returned to mathematics and code to analyse massive datasets. According to this scheme, graphs would belong to a pre-digital era, however, the conceptual problems they raised were closer to that of the second digital turn: logic, mathematics, structuring data not only pertain to recent debate on digital design, but they also confront, again, the tension between the non-visual aspects mathematics and the retinal qualities of architectural representation and design. *Graph Vision* offers a detailed overview of a set of concerns that still animates the contemporary discourse: these are issues related to counting, searching, systematising large sets of objects, as well as the primacy of deductive over inductive reasoning methods to define what intelligence might mean in design (which the book brilliantly captures in the analysis of the differences between

² T. Vardouli, *Graph Vision*, p. 180.

“specification” and “recognition” in the work of, respectively, Friedman and Negroponte-Groisser).

The pre-digital work on graphs also offers other elements of reflections that remind us that some issues in computational design persist regardless of technological change. One such theme is the role of the architect *vis-à-vis* the introduction of computers. Vardouli recalls how Friedman and later Negroponte designed different modes of interaction between architects and machines. Whereas Yona Friedman tasked computers to map out all the possibilities from which end users would choose, Negroponte’s YONA—a computer program inspired by Friedman’s work—allowed users to directly see the graphs, presenting them as “a malleable, visual entity, accessible well outside the cycles of a mathematical elite.”³ Contrary to the recent abundance of processing power, the research on graphs was characterised by technological scarcity. The limited computational capacities of mainframe computers of the 1960s and 1970s demanded a relentless, almost heroic, effort to simplify calculations to avoid so-called combinatorial explosion (the exponential growth of combinations caused by a linear increase of parameters). Graphs offer a highly economic way to represent architecture for a computer; they could recode an architectural plan through a limited set of numbers, disregarding geometrical information. They also framed architectural intelligence as largely a deductive problem. It is interesting to observe the contrast with the paradigm guiding the current generation of Artificial Intelligence which is trained on large datasets and partially grounds its intelligence in inductive operations.

Finally, in the midst of the integration of large language models (LLMs) in architecture, Vardouli reminds us that digital architecture had already flirted with language before. From George Stiny’s *Shape Grammar*—influenced by Chomsky’s generative grammar—to diagrammatic use of graphs by C. S. Peirce, proto-graph methods to analyse language had already been devised. Their abstract qualities responded to the crisis of empirical methods by substituting them with logical methods. The domain of references mobilised to chart the relation between language, architecture, and computation reinforces the impression that graphs were largely an Anglo-Saxon affair. The vast majority of the experiments and discussions took place either in the United States or England. The work of linguists from the Slavic regions seemed to have had little to no

³ T. Vardouli, *Graph Vision*, p. 182.

impact on the formalisation of architecture through graphs. As a result, the pool of references to draw from seemed to be determined earlier on and was never really questioned (perhaps, with the exception of Stiny's *Shape Grammar*). Perhaps as a consequence of this, the perimeter of the architectural issues and concerns attended through graphs also remained unchanged throughout some twenty years of research (plans constituted the main focus of the research).

Theodora Vardouli's *Graph Vision* offers a compelling, painstakingly detailed, and elegant overview of a period in architectural research which, at first glance, would appear far removed from the technological condition we inhabit. Through a closer inspection, however, we observe not only the persistence of recurrent themes—mathematics, philosophy, design's political agency—but also the importance of having a *vision*: graphs were the instruments and the instigators of a larger intellectual project that questioned architecture's role in society. A reminder that digital architecture was never just about technology.

